

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF *STREPTOGONOPUS PHIPSONI* (MILLIPEDES). PART I

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Streptogonopus phipsoni (Millipedes) belongs to the family of *Strongylosomadae*. The worms are generally 25 mm. in length and 2.6-3 mm. in width in the case of males and 3.6 mm.

in the case of females. The head, trunk and legs are of a bright dark chestnut colour in adults and pinkish red in the young ones. The pink colour changes to dark brown on exposure to light. The body consists of segments which are constricted in the suture and the male has got thicker legs. They are found in the United Provinces, Bihar, Punjab, and Bombay etc. (Pocock, *J. Bombay Nat. Hist. Soc.*, 1892, 7, 151; Attems, *Arch. Naturg.*, 1914, LXXX, A 4, p. 219) (Figs. 1 and 2).

During rainy season the worms attracted our attention and as no information was available they were subjected to a chemical examination. The worms come out in large numbers with rains and disappear at the close of the rainy season after producing two breeds. On keeping in *vacuo* over sulphuric acid they turn brittle but on re-exposing to air only the females come to life. They show moisture (51.4%) and in the ash (62.3% on the weight of dry animals) sodium, potassium, iron, magnesium, calcium, silica, sulphate, chloride and carbonate have been detected. On extraction with alcohol a protein is obtained showing proteinous nitrogen (52.06%) and xanthoprotein reaction and also a ruby-red to brown oil from which dimethylglyoxime has been separated. The isolation of this substance from millipedes marks the first instance where an oxime has been obtained from a living organism. As regards its occurrence there are three possibilities *viz.*, (i) it occurs as such, (ii) it is a decomposition product, (iii) it is a product of resynthesis. Future work will clear this point and therapeutic studies will decide its utility in medicine.

EXPERIMENTAL

A few hundred pairs of adult millipedes were picked and kept in a glass basin with earth and grass. It was noticed that from time to time the males were cast off dead by the females

Fig. 1.

S. Phipsoni (*Losomadae*) a, b, male ;
c, d, female ; e, mating.

Fig. 2.

S. Phipsoni (*Losomadae*) female.

and they went in search of new ones. They seem to hate intense sunlight but come out in the mornings and evenings in an orderly manner to a neat place and on being touched or disturbed they move very quickly in disorder in all directions. They emit a nauseating odour and secrete a bad-smelling fluid which does not produce any irritating effect or blisters on hands. The odourous principle is volatile with steam. The pink colour of the young breed changes to dark brown on exposure to light and with age.

About two dozen mating pairs were kept in *vacuo* over sulphuric acid when the males began to separate from the females and soon all turned brittle. After 15 minutes they were taken out from the desiccator and exposed to the air. After half an hour the females began to show signs of life and within two hours 90% began to move while none of the males showed any sign of life and remained brittle.

A representative sample of hundred worms was taken and was freed of adhering earth by washing with water. The worms were dried in *vacuo* at 100° and the dried worms were converted into ash (Table I), which indicated the presence of sodium, potassium, iron, calcium, magnesium, silica, sulphate, chloride and carbonate. It is difficult to say whether these constituents form part of millipedes or are derived from the unassimilated matter of the alimentary canal. A dissection of the worms would decide this. The worms on extraction with various solvents gave the following percentages of the extractables.

TABLE I

Moisture	... 51.4%
Ash on dry worms	... 62.3
Water-soluble ash	... 11.6
Sodium in water soluble ash °	... 2.7
Potassium in water-soluble ash †	... 3.27

TABLE II

Solvent,	
Ether	... 4.05%
Acetone	... 2.7
Chloroform	... 2.58
Benzene	... 1.171
Petroleum ether	... 1.50

Extraction of worms with Alcohol.—The worms (300 g.) were washed with water and percolated with alcohol (500 c.c.) for 72 hours. They were next extracted with alcohol on the water-bath for 6 hours. The combined extracts on standing deposited a pinkish sediment which on washing with ether turned as a dull white amorphous mass (A). The alcoholic filtrate was concentrated to 100 c.c. in *vacuo* and gave no deposit on keeping at 0° and was shaken with ether (5 times). The ether solution after washing and drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate gave viscous oily liquid (B). The immiscible liquid on treatment with neutral lead acetate yielded a lead salt which after deleading in alcoholic solution gave a small quantity of a brown sticky residue.

Fraction (A) was obtained as an amorphous powder (2 g.) and was insoluble in common organic solvents. It did not melt below 300° and showed absence of sulphur, phosphorus, and gave nitrogen by Kjeldal's method (8.33%) (52.06% as protein when 6.25 was used as factor). It gave xanthoprotein reaction and decolourised 5% solution of potassium permanganate. When warmed with concentrated sulphuric acid it turned deep brown while with concentrated sulphuric acid and potassium dichromate it gave a green solution in the cold which turned deep green on warming.

* By uranyl zinc acetate method, "Organic Reagents for Metals & for Certain Acid Radicals" by the Staff of the Research Laboratory of Hopkins and Williams Ltd, 3rd. edition, 1938 (London).

† By perchlorate method, W.A. Davis, *J. Agric. Sci.*, 1912 15, 52.

Fraction (B) was soluble in common organic solvents and gave a positive test for nitrogen. It was extracted (10 g.) with 10% hydrochloric acid but the acid solution on neutralisation with sodium carbonate gave only a faint turbidity. The acid-insoluble fraction was extracted with 5% sodium carbonate solution. The alkaline solution on neutralisation with 10% hydrochloric acid gave olive-green precipitate which was partly soluble in ether (1.5 g., insol., 0.7 g.). The alkali-insoluble residue was taken up in ether and after washing with water was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was removed and the residue on keeping at 0° deposited a crystalline mass [0.22g. 0.06% on the wt. of worms or 3.1% on the wt. of oily substance (B)]. It was soluble in alcohol, ether and acetone but insoluble in petroleum ether and crystallised from alcohol in bunches or needles, m. p. 234-35° (Fig. 3). Its solution tinged nickel spatula pink and this suggested its resemblance with dimethylglyoxime and led to its identification. It did not give any depression with an authentic sample of dimethylglyoxime, m.p. 234-35° [m.p. 234-35°, Dictionary of Applied Chemistry by Thorpe, Vol. IV, p. 6, (1940); m.p. 234, Organic Chemistry by Perkin and Kipping, Vol. III, p. 745, (1934); m.p. 245-46°, Meyer-Jacobson, I, (ii), 826, (1913)] and gave metallic complexes identical with those obtained with the synthetical samples (Table III). (Found in material dried at 100°: N, 24.08. Calc. for $C_4H_8O_2N_2$: N, 24.13 per cent).

Fig. 3. Dimethylglyoxime (m. p. 234-235°)
(146 times mag.)

TABLE III

Metallic complexes with dimethylglyoxime

Reagents.	Dimethylglyoxime : isolated sample.			Dimethylglyoxime : synthetic sample.		
	1%	5%	20%	1%	5%	20%
Nickel chloride	Pink ppt.	Red ppt.	Dark red ppt.	Pink ppt.	Red ppt.	Dark red ppt.
Bismuth nitrate	Yellow ppt	Yellow ppt.	Yellow ppt.	Yellow ppt.	Yellow ppt.	Yellow ppt.
Ferrous sulphate	Pink soln.	Pink soln. and violet ppt.	Pink soln.	Pink soln.	Pink soln. & violet ppt.	Pink soln & deep. violet ppt.

The filtrate from dimethylglyoxime yielded a brown residue, a portion of which dissolved in hot alcohol and crystallised in needles but could not be isolated in a state of purity. Alcohol-insoluble portion was not examined.

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